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FORMULATION AND DESIGN OF TASTE MASKED QUETIAPINE FUMARATE ORALLY FAST DISINTEGRATING TABLETS BY SUBLIMATION METHOD

Mettu Srikanth Reddy¹, N. G. Raghavendra Rao^{*1}, Krishna. D²

¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Jyothishmathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Thimmapur, Karimnagar - 505481, AP, India.

²Department of Pharmaceutics, St. Peter's Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Warangal -506001, AP, India.

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ABSTRACT

Quetiapine Fumarate bioavailability is 9%. Used in the treatment of schizophrenia. It is preferable to administer in the form of fast disintegrating tablets used for depressive episodes, acute manic episodes associated with [bipolar I disorder](#) at a short time. In present research work an attempt has been made to prepare taste masked fast dissolving tablets of Quetiapine Fumarate were prepared by using sublimation method. Crosspovidone is used as a superdisintegrant. Camphor, Urea and Menthol are used as a sublimating agent. The prepared tablets were evaluated for various parameters like weight variation, hardness, friability, disintegration time, drug content, water absorption ratio, wetting time, *in-vitro* drug release, FTIR studies and short term stability studies. IR spectral analysis study showed that there was no drug interaction with formulation additives of the tablet. The blend was examined for the pre-compressional parameters. The prepared tablets formulations were evaluated for post-compressional parameters. The values of pre-compression parameters evaluated were within prescribed limits and indicated good free flowing property. All the post-compressional parameter are evaluated were prescribed limits and results were within IP acceptable limits. The disintegration time of 15 to 68 sec, water absorption ratio of 66.75 to 83.52%, wetting time of 32 to 61.22 sec. *In-vitro* dissolution studies of all the formulations were carried various dissolution parameter values viz., percent drug dissolved in 4 min, 8 min, 12 min, 16 min, 20 min, 24 min, and 28min (D₄, D₈, D₁₂, D₁₆, D₂₀, D₂₄, and D₂₈), t_{50%} and t_{90%}. This data reveals that overall, the formulation SQF1, SQF2, SQF3 and SQF9 shows nearly faster drug release. The formulations SQF1, SQF2, SQF3 and SQF9 50 % of drug released in 0.92 min, 0.80min, 0.65 min, and 0.86 min respectively, and 90 % of drug released in 5.90 min, 4.88 min, 2.89 min and 6.98 min, respectively when compared to other tablet formulation. Among all the formulation SQF3 were found to be promising and showed a disintegration time of 15 sec, 50 % of drug released in 0.65 min, and 90 % of drug released in 2.89 min. The results obtained showed that the quantity of Crosspovidone and camphor significantly affect response variables. The stability study conducted as per the ICH guidelines and the formulations were found to be stable. The results concluded that fast dissolving tablets Quetiapine Fumarate showing enhanced dissolution, will lead to improved bioavailability, improved effectiveness and hence better patient compliance.

Corresponding author: Dr. N. G. Raghavendra Rao, Principal and HOD, Jyothishmathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, Ramakrishna Colony,

Thimmapur, KARIMNAGAR-505481, Andhra Pradesh, Mob No: +919966794479, +919448570193

Email: nraghu@rediffmail.com

INTRODUCTION:

Quetiapine Fumarate bioavailability is 9%. Half-life of drug is Approximately 6 hrs. Quetiapine Fumarate is a psychotropic agent belonging to a chemical class, the dibenzothiazepine derivatives. Used in the treatment of schizophrenia. It is preferable to administer in the form of fast disintegrating tablets used for depressive episodes, acute manic episodes associated with [bipolar I disorder](#) at a short time¹⁻³.

Most pharmaceutical forms for oral administration are formulated for direct ingestion, for chewing, for prior dispersion and /or dissolution in water; some of them are absorbed in mouth (sublingual or buccal tablets). Elderly individuals have difficulty in swallowing when prescribed in conventional tablet and capsule form⁴⁻⁶. The problem of swallowing is also evident in pediatrics, psychiatric as well as travelling patients who may not have ready access to water⁷. The rapidly disintegrating tablet in mouth or oro dispersible tablets overcome all the above problems and thus offer an alternate form of oral medication, which provide patients with a more convenient means of taking their medication⁸. Addition of super disintegrating agent in the formulation is one of the approaches to formulate oro dispersible tablets⁹⁻¹⁵.

Orally Disintegrating tablets (ODTs) rapidly disintegrate in the mouth without chewing upon oral administration and without the need for water, unlike other drug delivery systems and conventional oral solid immediate-release dosage form. ODT dosage forms, also commonly known as fast melt, quick melts, fast disintegrating and orodispersible systems have the unique property of disintegrating the tablet in the mouth in sec.

The desired criteria for the FDT they should Have a pleasing mouth feel, Leave minimal or no residue in the mouth after oral administration and not require water to swallow, but it should dissolve or disintegrate in the mouth in a matter of sec¹⁶⁻¹⁷. Most commonly used methods to prepare these tablets are; freeze-drying/Lyophilization¹⁸ tablet molding¹⁹ and direct-compression methods²⁰. Lyophilized tablets show a very porous structure, which causes quick penetration of saliva into the pores when placed in oral cavity^{18,21}. Moulded tablets dissolve completely and rapidly. However, lack of strength and taste masking are of great concern²². Main advantages of direct compression are low manufacturing cost and high mechanical integrity of the tablets²³. Therefore, direct-compression appears to be a better option for manufacturing of tablets.

In present research work an attempt has been made to prepare fast dissolving tablets of Quetiapine Fumarate by using sublimation method. The fast disintegrating tablets are prepared by sublimation method, in general based on the action established by superdisintegrant such as Crosspovidone and sublimating agents such as camphor, urea and menthol. Effects of sublimated tablets (Drug, polymer and sublimating agent) on wetting time, disintegrating time, drug content, in-vitro release, and stability studies parameters have been studied.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

Materials:

Quetiapine Fumarate was procured from Gift sample from Aan Pharma Ltd. Gujarat. Crosspovidone was procured as a gift sample from Signet (Mumbai), Mannitol, MCC, aspartame, talc and magnesium stearate purchased from S.D. Fine chem., Mumbai. All other materials were of analytical reagent grade.

Preparation of Drug Polymer Complex:

Quetiapine Fumarate and Eudragit E100 complex was prepared by solvent evaporation method. Saturated stock solutions of Quetiapine Fumarate and Eudragit E100 were prepared in absolute Ethanol. Aliquots of drug and polymer solutions were taken to obtain various ratios (1:0.5, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3) and mixed continuously at 150 rpm on a magnetic stirrer. Stirring was allowed to continue until the solvent is completely evaporated. After this

mixture was kept at 35°C for 2 hours and dried under vacuum for 24 hrs to obtain a hard matrix. Then the hard matrix is subsequently pulverized and screened through 60 mesh to obtain the uniform sized fine powder of drug polymer complex (DPC) and it was finally stored in a tightly closed container for further studies.

Taste evaluation:

Taste evaluation was performed on six healthy human volunteers for pure drug, and for four different ratios of drug: polymer. Bitterness was recorded immediately and at several intervals for 5 min according to the bitterness intensity scale from 0 to 5 where 0, 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 indicate no, threshold, slight, moderate, and strong bitterness.

Preparation of fast dissolving tablets by direct compression technique²⁴:

The basic principle involved in preparing fast dissolving tablets by sublimation technique shown in **Fig 1** using inert sublimating agents and crosspovidone were added to other tablet excipients and the blend was compressed into tablet. Removal of volatile material by sublimation generated a porous structure. Accurately weighed ingredients were sifted through sieve no.44 and thoroughly mixed for 10 min and magnesium stearate and other ingredients were added to the blend and thoroughly mixed. The tablets were compressed using Rimek tablet punching machine. The composition of the tablets was given in **Table 1**. The compressed tablets were then subjected to sublimation at 50°C for 60 min. The tablets were evaluated for disintegration time and mean tablet weight. The tablets dissolve within 10-20 sec. and exhibit sufficient mechanical strength for practical use.

Fig 1: Schematics figure of Sublimation method for design of Mouth dissolving tablets

Table 1: Formulation of Quetiapine Fumarate fast dissolving tablets prepared by sublimation method (1-tablets)

Ingredient (mg)	Formulation code								
	SQF1	SQF2	SQF3	SQF4	SQF5	SQF6	SQF7	SQF8	SQF9
QF	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
CP	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24
Camphor	10	15	20	--	--	--	--	--	--
Urea	--	--	--	10	15	20	--	--	--
Menthol	--	--	--	--	--	--	10	15	20
Aspartame	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
D-M	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
MCC	47	42	37	47	42	37	47	42	37
P V P	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Talc	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Mg St	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

Note: QF=Quetiapine Fumarate, CP=Crosspovidone, D-M=D-Mannitol, MCC=Microcrystalline cellulose (Avicel PH-102), Mg St= Magnesium stearate.

After compression the tablets were collected and vacuum dried in a vacuum oven at 80° C until a constant weight was obtained to ensure the complete removal of sublimable component to make the tablet porous (Table 2).

Evaluation of Quetiapine Fumarate tablets:

Micromeritic properties of powder blend of tablets before compression: the prepared tablet blends are evaluated for different tests like angle of repose, apparent bulk density, tapped density, percent compressibility and Hausner ratio,

Evaluation of Tasted masked Quetiapine Fumarate Fast Disintegrating Tablets²⁵⁻²⁸:

Weight variation: Average weight of 20 tablets is calculated using an electronic balance. Individual weight of each tablet is calculated and compared with the average weight. The Mean \pm SD and RSD were noted. The tablets meet USP specifications if no more than 2 tablets outside the percentage limit and if no tablet differs by more than 2 times the percentage limit.

Tablet Thickness: Randomly 10 tablets should be taken and thickness was measured for each tablet by placing it between two anvils and rotating the sliding knob until the tablet was tightly fitted and the reading was noted. The tablet thickness should be controlled within a $\pm 5\%$ variation of a standard value.

Hardness and Friability: Tablet hardness has been defined as “the force required to break a tablet in a diametric compression test”. To perform this test, the tablet is placed between two anvils, force is applied to the anvils, and the crushing strength that just causes the tablet to break is recorded. Hardness is thus sometimes called as “tablet crushing strength”. Several devices that commonly serve the purpose of determining the tablet hardness are the Monsanto tester, the Strong-cobb tester, the Pfizer tester, the Erweka tester and the Schleuniger tester.

Table 2: Tablet weight before vacuum drying (BVD) and after vacuum drying (AVD)

Formulation	Tablet Weight	
	BVD	AVD
SQF1	201 (0.54)	176 (0.63)
SQF2	200 (0.62)	180 (0.58)
SQF3	202 (0.34)	178 (0.68)
SQF4	199 (0.44)	161 (0.82)
SQF5	202 (0.67)	165 (0.92)
SQF6	200 (0.98)	158 (0.36)
SQF7	201 (0.28)	149 (0.72)
SQF8	200 (0.66)	152 (0.76)
SQF9	201 (0.92)	148 (0.64)

Hardness of tablet was determined by using a Monsanto tablet hardness tester (Cadmach Machinery Co, Ahmadabad, India). Friability of ten tablets from each formulation was determined using the Roche friabilator (Campbell Electronics, Mumbai, India). This device subjects a no of tablets to the combined effect of abrasions and shock by utilizing a plastic chamber that revolves at 25 rpm dropping the tablets at distance of 6 inches with each revolution. Pre-weighed sample of tablets was placed in the friabilator, which was then operated for 100 revolutions. Tablets were dusted and re-weighed.

Content uniformity: Six tablets from each formulation were taken randomly and powdered. A quantity of powder equivalent to weight of one tablet was transferred in to a 100mL volumetric flask, containing 0.1 N HCL and mixed thoroughly for few minutes and the volume was made up to 100mL with 0.1 N HCL. The solution was filtered through whatman filter paper and suitably diluted with the same medium and the drug content was estimated from the standard plot by measuring the absorbance at 290 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

In vitro disintegration time: *In vitro* disintegration time of FDTs was determined by following the procedure described in earlier reports (Gohel et al., 2004). Briefly 10 mL of 0.1N HCL at room temperature was taken in a petri dish of 10cm in diameter. The tablet was then carefully placed in the centre of petri dish and the time required for the tablet to completely disintegrate into fine particles was noted. Measurements were carried out in triplicates.

Wetting time and water absorption ratio: The wetting time of the tablets was measured using a simple procedure. Five circular tissue papers of 10-cm diameter were placed in a Petri dish with a 10-cm diameter. Ten milliliters of water containing a water-soluble dye was added to the petri dish. A tablet was carefully placed on the surface of tissue paper in the petri dish at room temperature. The time required for water to reach the upper surface of the tablets and completely wet them was noted as the wetting time. To check for reproducibility, the measurements were carried out (n=6) and the mean value was calculated.

The weight of the tablet before keeping in the petri dish was noted (W_b). The wetted tablet from the petri dish was taken and reweighed (W_a). The Water absorption ratio, R, was determined according to the following equation:

$$R = 100 (W_a - W_b) / W_b$$

Where W_b and W_a are the weight before and after water absorption respectively.

Measurement of wetting time of a tablet was shown in **Fig 2**.

Fig 2: Simple method for the measurement of wetting time of a tablet.

In vitro Dissolution Studies²⁹: The *in vitro* dissolution study of taste masked Quetiapine Fumarate FDTs were performed using USP type II (paddle) apparatus. The dissolution medium consists of 900mL of 0.1N HCL thermostated at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred continuously at 50 rpm through out the experiment. An aliquot of 5mL was collected at predetermined time intervals (5, 10, 20, 30, 45, 60 min) and replaced with fresh dissolution medium. The samples were filtered, by passing through 0.45 μm membrane filter and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 290 nm. Dissolution rate was studied for all designed formulations.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR): The chemical interaction between the drug and polymer was evaluated by subjecting drug, polymer, DPC to FTIR studies. FTIR spectra were obtained on Shimadzu

FTIR (Shimadzu Corp., India). Samples were prepared in KBr disks, the scanning range was 4000 and 400 cm^{-1} .

The stability study of the tablets was carried out according to International conference on Harmonization guidelines for zone III and IV. The formulations were stored at (25°C/60% RH) and (40°C/75% RH for three months by storing the samples in stability chamber (Thermo Lab, Mumbai). The promising formulations were subjected to short term stability study. The formulations SQF3, SQF6 and SQF9 were selected.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Taste evaluation: Taste evaluation was performed on six healthy human volunteers and the results were reported in the **Table 3**. The pure drug was felt bitter immediately after it was kept on the tongue and the sense was even carried up to 5 min. However the bitterness of the drug was reduced or even masked after complexation with eudragit EPO in different ratios (1:0.5, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3). In case of 1: 0.5 ratio it was felt slightly bitter after 1 min and it is apparent from the results that the increasing concentrations of the polymer have completely have completely masked the bitter taste of the drug. Since the drug is not in the native form and entrapped with in the polymeric matrix, and there by reduction in the solubility of the drug in the saliva could have led to the masking of the bitter taste. Even though the Quetiapine Fumarate taste was masked with drug polymer complex (1:0.5, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3) ratios, we have selected 1:1 for further studies, since higher amounts of polymer may retard the dissolution performance of the final fast disintegrating tablets of Quetiapine Fumarate. Erythritol (1%w/w) was included in all the formulations to improve the palatability.

Table 3: comparative taste evaluation.

Form of Quetiapine Fumarate	10 sec	30 sec	1 min	2 min	5 min
Pure drug	3	3	3	3	2
DPC (1:0.5)	0.5	1	1	1	0
DPC (1:1)	0	0	0.5	0.5	0
DPC (1:2)	0	0	0.5	0	0
DPC (1:3)	0	0	0.5	0	0

The values of pre-compression parameters evaluated were within prescribed limits and indicated good free flowing property (**Table 4**). All the post compressional parameter are evaluated were prescribed limits and results were within IP acceptable limits. Results were shown in (**Table 5**). In all the formulations, hardness test indicated good mechanical strength ranges from 2.6 to 3.3kg/cm².The friability range is 0.63 to 0.74 % to be well within the approved range (<1%)indicated that tablet had good mechanical resistance. The weight variation was found in all designed formulations in the range 195 to 200 mg. All the tablets passed weight variation test as the average percentage weight variation was within 7.5% i.e.in the pharmacopoeia limits. The thickness was almost uniform in all the formulations and values ranged from 3.48 mm to 3.74 mm. The standard deviation values indicated that all the formulations were within the range. Rapid disintegration within several minutes was observed in all the formulations. The *in-vitro* disintegration data is tabulated in the (**Table 6**) and **Fig 3**. The *in-*

in vitro disintegration time of fast dissolving tablets were found to be 15 to 68 sec. which is in the range of fulfilling the official requirements. By the addition of superdisintegrants the disintegration time increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) tablets prepared. Based on the *in-vitro* disintegration time, formulation SQF3 were found to be promising and showed a disintegration time of 15 sec. These results suggest that the disintegration times can be decreased by using wicking type disintegrants (Crosspovidone). Wetting time is closely related to the inner structure of the tablet. The wetting time of Quetiapine Fumarate tablets were found to be in the range of 22.62 to 88.62 sec. The water absorption ratio in the range 71.32 to 84.41%. The percentage drugs content of the tablets were found to be between 97.46 to 99.66% of Quetiapine Fumarate. The results were within the range and that indicated uniformity of mixing. The wetting time, water absorption ratios and drug content results were tabulated in the Table 6.

Table 4: Pre-compression parameters Quetiapine Fumarate fast dissolving tablets.

Formulation code	Angle of Repose (°)	Bulk Density (gm/cm ³)	Tapped Density (gm/cm ³)	Percent Compressibility Index (I)	Hausner's Ratio
SQF1	36.4	0.48	0.62	22.58	1.29
SQF2	37.2	0.51	0.61	16.39	1.19
SQF3	37.5	0.49	0.6	18.33	1.22
SQF4	33.2	0.5	0.58	13.79	1.16
SQF5	30.5	0.48	0.58	17.24	1.20
SQF6	26.8	0.51	0.59	13.55	1.15
SQF7	27.4	0.52	0.59	11.86	1.13
SQF8	30.2	0.50	0.60	16.66	1.20
SQF9	26.3	0.48	0.62	22.58	1.29

* Average of three determinations

Table 5: Post-compression parameters Quetiapine Fumarate fast dissolving tablets

FC	Hardness* (Kg/cm ²) ± SD	Friability (%)	Thickness* (mm) ± SD	Weight variation* (mg) ± SD
SQF1	3.2 ± 0.16	0.63 ± 0.02	3.64 ± 0.12	200.00 ± 1.2
SQF2	3.1 ± 0.15	0.65 ± 0.06	3.48 ± 0.14	198.32 ± 1.6
SQF3	2.6 ± 0.12	0.68 ± 0.12	3.52 ± 0.12	199.98 ± 1.2
SQF4	3.2 ± 0.14	0.69 ± 0.06	3.62 ± 0.14	199.42 ± 1.0
SQF5	2.7 ± 0.12	0.68 ± 0.14	3.72 ± 0.5	198.75 ± 0.6
SQF6	2.8 ± 0.16	0.70 ± 0.12	3.66 ± 0.12	199.59 ± 1.2
SQF7	2.9 ± 0.12	0.72 ± 0.18	3.74 ± 0.14	199.99 ± 1.6
SQF8	3.1 ± 0.22	0.71 ± 0.12	3.48 ± 0.06	199.54 ± 1.2
SQF9	3.3 ± 0.14	0.74 ± 0.14	3.62 ± 0.12	197.84 ± 1.6

* Average of three determinations

Table 6: Post-compression parameters Quetiapine Fumarate fast dissolving tablets

FC	Disintegration time* (sec) \pm SD	Wetting time* (sec) \pm SD	Water absorption ratio* \pm SD	Drug Content* (%) \pm SD
SQF1	27.02 \pm 1.2	28.42 \pm 1.2	84.41 \pm 1.4	99.66 \pm 1.1
SQF2	22.60 \pm 0.8	24.41 \pm 1.2	82.98 \pm 1.2	98.42 \pm 1.2
SQF3	15.12 \pm 0.9	22.62 \pm 1.2	80.43 \pm 1.4	99.24 \pm 1.4
SQF4	68.01 \pm 1.4	88.62 \pm 0.8	78.32 \pm 1.0	97.88 \pm 0.4
SQF5	49.36 \pm 1.2	74.32 \pm 0.4	75.32 \pm 1.2	99.46 \pm 0.2
SQF6	38.46 \pm 1.6	33.62 \pm 1.2	71.87 \pm 1.4	98.50 \pm 1.2
SQF7	39.84 \pm 1.2	38.14 \pm 1.2	75.50 \pm 1.6	97.46 \pm 1.1
SQF8	28.46 \pm 0.6	30.34 \pm 1.4	72.42 \pm 1.4	97.88 \pm 0.2
SQF9	21.62 \pm 0.8	25.31 \pm 0.6	71.32 \pm 1.2	98.74 \pm 1.2

* Average of three determinations

Fig 3: Disintegration time v/s. Formulation (SQF1 – SQF9).

In-vitro dissolution studies of all the formulations were carried out in 0.1N HCL, the release results were shown in **Figs 4-6**. All the formulations were carried out various dissolution parameter values viz., percent drug dissolved in 4 min, 8 min, 12 min, 16 min, 20 min, 24 min, and 28min (D₄, D₈, D₁₂, D₁₆, D₂₀, D₂₄, and D₂₈),

$t_{50\%}$ and $t_{90\%}$ are shown in **Table 7**. This data reveals that overall, the formulation SQF1, SQF2, SQF3 and SQF9 shows nearly faster drug release.

The formulations SQF1, SQF2, SQF3 and SQF9 50 % of drug released in 0.92 min, 0.80min, 0.65 min, and 0.86 min respectively, and 90 % of drug released in 5.90 min, 4.88 min, 2.89 min and 6.98 min, respectively when compared to other tablet formulation. Among all the formulation SQF3 were found to be promising and showed a disintegration time of 15 sec, 50 % of drug released in 0.65 min, and 90 % of drug released in 2.89 min.

The **Table 8** shows the parameters of the tablets after stability study. The promising formulations were subjected to short term stability study by storing the formulations at 25°C/65% and 40°C/75% RH up to three month. The formulations SQF3, SQF6 and SQF9 were selected. After three month the tablets were again analyzed for the hardness, friability, drug content uniformity and disintegration time. Decrease in the disintegration time was observed in tablets prepared by camphor sublimation method. Since during the preparation of tablets by camphor sublimation method, only 6 hrs at 50°C was used, where as 90 days and 45°C were used during stability studies.

Fig 4: Release profile of formulation containing camphor (SQF1-SQF3)

Fig 5: Release profile of formulation containing urea (SQF4-SQF6)

Fig 6: Release profile of formulation containing menthol (SQF7-SQF9)

Table 7: In-vitro release profile of Quetiapine Fumarate fast dissolving Tablets

FC	Parameters								
	D ₄	D ₈	D ₁₂	D ₁₆	D ₂₀	D ₂₄	D ₂₈	D t _{50%}	D t _{90%}
SQF1	74.87	96.73	--	--	--	--	--	0.92 min	5.90 min
SQF2	85.75	99.93	--	--	--	--	--	0.80 min	4.88 min
SQF3	97.40	--	--	--	--	--	--	0.65 min	2.89 min
SQF4	47.95	57.57	67.31	74.77	83.40	91.58	98.02	5.69 min	23.58 min
SQF5	52.33	61.64	71.06	79.84	92.88	99.88	--	3.82 min	19.38 min
SQF6	61.82	73.42	84.05	93.15	99.80	--	--	1.81 min	15.4 min
SQF7	64.17	80.04	94.59	--	--	--	--	1.96 min	10.81 min
SQF8	67.15	87.64	99.23	--	--	--	--	1.00 min	8.95 min
SQF9	74.18	94.30	--	--	--	--	--	0.86 min	6.98 min

In the present study the IR spectra for pure drug Quetiapine Fumarate and its formulations with various polymers and other excipients is taken to establish the physical characterization of drug and its formulations (Fig 7). FTIR analysis was used to study the possible chemical interaction between the drug and polymer. The pure drug which is an dibenzothiazepine derivatives showed a characteristic peak at 3317.5 cm^{-1} this is due to N-H stretching and peaks at 1598.99 cm^{-1} and 1571.99 cm^{-1} indicative of the N-H deformation. The peak at 1336.67 cm^{-1} is due to the C-O stretching and peaks at 1458.18 cm^{-1} and 1413.82 cm^{-1} are indicative of C=C stretching of aromatic nucleus. Eudragit E100 which is an methacrylic acid ester showed important peaks at 1732.08 cm^{-1} indicative of C=O stretch of the ester group. The peaks at 2954.95 cm^{-1} indicative of C-H stretch in the alkane and 2769.78 cm^{-1} and 2821.86 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the dimethyl amino group.

The FTIR spectra of Drug Polymer Complex (DPC) displayed all the characteristic peaks of both drug and polymer. The N-H and C-O stretch band of drug and C=O stretch and C-H stretch in dimethyl amino group and C-H stretch in alkane of the polymer bands were detected in the same position. Consequently the FTIR of DPC and physical mixture seemed to be summation of drug and eudragit E100. The physical mixture showed additional characteristic peak at 3385.07 cm^{-1} indicative of free O-H stretch. Overall there was no alteration in the characteristic peaks of drug and polymer in the DPC suggesting that there was no interaction between the drug and polymer.

Table 8: Result for promising Quetiapine Fumarate fast dissolving tablets at (25°C/60% RH) and (40°C/75% RH) for 3 months.

Sl. No.	FC	Month	Hardness Kg/cm ²	percentage Friability	Dispersion time (sec)
(25°C/60% RH)					
1	SQF1	1 st	3.2	0.63	27.02
		2 nd	3.2	0.64	28.14
		3 rd	3.3	0.65	29.06
2	SQF2	1 st	3.1	0.65	22.60
		2 nd	3.1	0.66	23.34
		3 rd	3.3	0.67	24.46
3	SQF3	1 st	2.6	0.68	15.12
		2 nd	2.8	0.69	16.22
		3 rd	2.8	0.70	17.46
4	SQF9	1 st	3.3	0.74	21.62
		2 nd	3.4	0.73	22.42
		3 rd	3.4	0.75	23.64
(40°C/75% RH)					
5	SQF1	1 st	3.2	0.63	27.02
		2 nd	3.3	0.65	28.42
		3 rd	3.4	0.66	29.32
6	SQF2	1 st	3.1	0.65	22.60
		2 nd	3.2	0.67	23.44
		3 rd	3.3	0.67	24.62
7	SQF3	1 st	2.6	0.68	15.12
		2 nd	2.7	0.69	16.64
		3 rd	2.9	0.71	17.82
8	SQF9	1 st	3.3	0.74	21.62
		2 nd	3.4	0.72	22.21
		3 rd	3.5	0.75	23.82

Fig 7: FTIR spectra of pure drug Quetiapine Fumarate and formulations SQF1, SQF2, SQF3 and SQF9.

CONCLUSION:

The above results concluded that, although differences existed between the superdisintegrants, the fast dissolving Quetiapine Fumarate tablets could be prepared by using any of the superdisintegrants used. Overall results indicates that formulation SQF3 which contain 15% Crosspovidone and camphor was better one and satisfies all the criteria as fast dissolving tablet. Quetiapine Fumarate showing enhanced dissolution, may lead to improved bioavailability, improved effectiveness and hence better patient compliance.

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